

Embioptera

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Clothodidae: *Clothoda longicauda* Ross

Embryos are Plecoptera.

Relationship:

- Presence of
- ① stem of M
 - ② stem of Cu
 - ③ fusion ~~temporary~~ between RP and MA
 - ④ indicate close relation to Plecoptera

Symplesiomorphic

HW has anal lobe including AA+2 as in Orthoptera (and Embioneoptera)

ScA well preserved and long as in many Cyrtoptera!

BUT: Stem of Cu present (absent in Orth); fusion RP & MA present; CuP similar

Embioptera: Clothodidae: *Clothoda longicauda* Ross

ScA+ runs on top of reduced ScP-

1. CuA and CuP closely parallel near base
2. RP and MA adjacent at length
3. Arculus is present

The prominent plesiotaxon Paolioidea (Carboniferous, Permian) of Neoptera shares with Embioptera characters 1, 2, 3!

Embioptera: Clothodidae: *Clothoda longicauda*

Wings evolved from the first leg segment, the epicoxa and its exite. The flattened epicoxa became the articular sclerites of the proxalaria (PR) and axalaria (AX), the exite base the fulcalaria (F), and the rest of the exite became the muscle-less wing blade. The epicoxa occurs on all serially homologous body segments of the head, thorax, and abdomen (see text and examples).

Embioptera: Clothodidae: *Clothoda longicauda*

Wing variations:

CLOTHODIDAE: *Clothoda longicauda* Ross

FW♂

IMPORTANT: very primitive flapping flight!

Relationship: Embioptera are related to Elleoptera, belong to Plecoptera

- PC strip present ——— plesio at Neoptera
- Stem of M present ——— as only in Ortho and Plecoptera
- " " Cu present ——— as in Plecoptera
- FW: AA: reduced fusing branch ——— autapomorph
- RP & MA long fusion ——— as often in Plecoptera
- ScA well developed, long ——— as in Orthoneoptera; plesio at Neoptera level
- CuA simple, not forked, proximally running close to CuP ——— as in Plecoptera
- HW: only
- AA+2 prot reduced: anal lobe starts at CLAVAL flexion line — as in Pleco and Orthoptera

Clothodidae:
Clothoda nobilis
 Brazil

articulation
 similar to Plecoptera

Clothodidae: *Clothoda nobilis* Goerst Brazil

Clothodidae

FW Clothodidae? Burma (700 undescribed spp.)

Coll. Ross
San Francisco

FW

Clothodidae: *Clothoda nobilis*

Brazil

Why Embioptera belong to Pleconeoptera:

Stem of M present (as only in Plecoptera and Orthoptera)

Stem of Cu present (absent in Orthoptera)

Long fusion RP with MA, often in Plecoptera

CuP simple

CuA bowed, proximally runs close to CuP (very typical, also for fossil Paoliids)

HW anal lobe starts at claval line (as only in Plecoptera and Orthoptera)

Plesiomorphies: 1, PC strip present; 2, ScA long; 3, plesiotypic flight

Embiidae: *Archembia* sp.

Venezuela Coll. Ross

Family unknown: *Oligoembia buski* Ross

Panama

length 5.5 mm

So runs close to RA

length 4.4 mm

Family unknown: *Spathembia* sp.

Bolivia, St. Cruz

Coll. E. S. Ross

Fossil Embioptera related Carboniferous Paolioidea

WHAT ARE THEY??

PAOLIOIDEA: *Protoblattina bowieri* Meunier, 1909

France
Lourmen
Stephanian

- Prominent early NEOPTERA share with Embioptera:
- ① Presence of the stem of M;
 - ② long fusion between RP and MA
 - ③ short Cu followed by long parallel run of CuA and CuP
 - ④ presence of arculus
- Relationship is quite possible, and both groups probably belong to PLECO-NEOPTERA